

Historical and Contemporary Predictors of Regional Cultural Differences in Individualism-Collectivism in Russia

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Abstract

Grounded in the ecocultural framework, this study examines the historical and contemporary predictors of regional cultural differences in individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) across Russia, focusing on private land ownership in the late 19th and early 20th centuries and current employment in agriculture. The analysis reveals that regions with a higher prevalence of private land ownership in 1877 and 1905 exhibit stronger individualistic tendencies in modern times, suggesting a continuity of cultural traits. Additionally, contemporary factors such as the share of the workforce employed in agriculture and ethnic composition – particularly the proportion of ethnic Russians – emerge as significant predictors of IND–COL differences. However, urbanization shows no significant relationship with regional cultural variation in IND–COL, indicating that although it may correlate with individualism, it is not a primary predictor. The findings underscore that factors rooted in traditional subsistence strategies exert a profound and lasting influence on regional cultural differences, persisting even through the sweeping societal transformations of the Soviet era.

Keywords

regional culture, individualism–collectivism, subsistence strategies, private land ownership, agriculture, ethnic composition, urbanization, historical continuity

JEL codes: Q15, Q19, R59, Z13

Introduction

National cultural differences provide crucial insights into why countries vary in institutional quality and levels of economic development. A substantial body of research has focused on the individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) dimension, which captures a broad spectrum of cultural variation (Fog 2021; Fog 2023; Kaasa and Minkov 2022) and serves as a robust predictor of socioeconomic development (Hartinger et al. 2021). The IND–COL dimension reflects whether the primary unit of social interaction in a society is the individual or the group, shaping the evolution of social institutions that either foster social cohesion or promote individual autonomy governed by universal rules (Minkov et al. 2023a; see also Berry 1994).

Importantly, significant regional variations in IND–COL often diverge from national norms. Recent research challenges the traditional East–West framing of IND–COL, revealing that these cultural dimensions follow latitudinal gradients – from African countries at low latitudes to the United States at mid-latitudes and Russian regions at high latitudes (van de Vliert et al. 2025). This insight has spurred growing interest in studying regional cultures within individual countries, as this approach uncovers cultural patterns that might be overlooked in analyses limited to the national level. In relatively homogeneous countries such as Norway, examining national culture may suffice; however, in many heterogeneous countries, individual regions differ substantially. These pronounced regional differences often arise because national borders are frequently artificial constructs encompassing diverse ethnic, linguistic, and religious groups within a single state (Kaasa et al. 2013).

Moreover, large countries typically encompass diverse environmental and socioeconomic conditions, which can contribute to the formation of distinct regional cultural characteristics (Peterson et al. 2018). For instance, while residents of Shanghai and Beijing share the same national identity, historical differences in economic management have produced unique cultural traits that are not readily apparent at the national level (Ebert et al. 2024). To study cultures effectively across multiple levels, it is useful to conceptualize national cultures as gravitational fields influencing all residents of a country, though the strength of this influence varies according to regional characteristics (Akaliyski et al. 2021). Analyzing regional differences can also clarify how such differences may grow large enough to challenge the peaceful coexistence of regions within a country, as illustrated by cases such as Catalonia in Spain or Scotland in the United Kingdom (Ebert et al. 2024).

Russia represents a unique case, with its vast and diverse regions characterized by varying ecological conditions and distinct historical backgrounds. However, the sources of variation in regional cultural characteristics across Russia remain insufficiently explained. This paper seeks to address this gap by analyzing both historical and contemporary data to explore their relationship with current levels of individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) across Russian regions. Specifically, the study examines historical Russia – an agrarian society in which the majority of the population was engaged in farming – to investigate the association between the prevalence of private land ownership and contemporary IND–COL in these regions. Furthermore, the research explores whether current employment in agriculture correlates with regional cultural differences. Other factors closely linked to agriculture in Russia, such as urbanization and ethnic composition, are also considered in the analysis.

Culture serves as the foundation for a group's successful adaptation to specific ecological conditions (Berry 2019). The features of agricultural practices prevalent in a region can substantially influence cultural patterns. In regions where the primary crop is labor-intensive –

such as rice – collectivist orientations (COL) are more likely to emerge. This tendency can be attributed to several factors: maintaining complex irrigation systems requires coordinated group effort, and the effective organization of such work often depends on hierarchical structures with clear leadership (Ang 2019; Mishra and Berry 2017; Talhelm 2022; Talhelm and English 2020; Talhelm et al. 2014). The high labor demands of these agricultural systems necessitate sustained cooperative efforts throughout the year, fostering collectivist norms (Fiszbein et al. 2022). Such practices promote interdependence and mutual support among workers, reinforcing stable and cooperative group dynamics.

In contrast, agricultural practices characterized by lower labor intensity – requiring less coordination and more intermittent work – tend to foster individualism (IND). These systems do not require the same level of group stability and cohesion, thereby allowing for more independent modes of work.

While ecology plays a crucial role in shaping primary social institutions – such as systems of agriculture – these primary institutions, in turn, give rise to equally important secondary institutions, including norms of social governance and religious practices. These secondary institutions, which constitute broader socio-political contexts, often maintain continuity with modern cultural patterns (Berry 2018). Unlike other species, humans possess the unique capacity to construct cultural and ecological niches that shape the lifestyles and institutions of future generations (Ready and Price 2021).

Neglecting a broader historical perspective that connects the distant past with the present risks creating a disconnect between ecological and social explanations of cultural development (Atari and Henrich 2023; Muthukrishna et al. 2021). Moreover, substantial evidence suggests that historical institutional systems are closely linked to contemporary cultural orientations. Modern collectivist (COL) cultures often trace their roots to ancient economic systems characterized by the absence of private land ownership, centralized distribution of agricultural and industrial goods, underdeveloped markets, and state-controlled foreign trade. In contrast, individualist (IND) cultures have evolved from economies with private property rights and well-developed domestic and international markets (Roland 2020).

The institution of private property likely played a pivotal role in the development of WEIRD (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, and Democratic) societies. Contrary to the common assumption that the peasantry – typically associated with communal living and limited property ownership – was the dominant social class, a closer examination of English history reveals a different picture. By the late Middle Ages, independent farmers in England were already engaged in trade with one another (MacFarlane 1978). This form of agrarian organization may have served as a key mediating mechanism linking specific environmental conditions – such as those associated with the cool-water index (Welzel et al. 2025) – to the emergence of “WEIRDness” in modern England.

Historical changes in agricultural labor intensity brought about by mechanization have also profoundly influenced cultural orientations (Fiszbein et al. 2022). Mechanization reduced the need for coordinated group labor, thereby fostering more individualistic tendencies as reliance on collective effort declined. For instance, regions that transitioned from labor-intensive crops such as cotton to less labor-intensive crops such as wheat – whether due to mechanization or pest infestations – experienced a notable shift toward greater individualism.

A study by Minkov et al. (2023b) on regional differences in individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) in Russia further supports the concept of “regional culture” as a meaningful analytical framework. Specifically, these regional variations in IND–COL were associated

with differences in electoral behavior and political protest activity (Gallyamova and Miller 2024). In addition, several studies have examined the historical continuity between the social structures of the Russian Empire and those of modern Russia. For example, in regions where nuclear family structures predominated according to the 1897 census, residents were more likely to support democratic candidates in the 1917 elections to the Constituent Assembly (favoring the Kadet Party) as well as in the presidential elections between 1996 and 2000 (supporting Grigory Yavlinsky) (Kravtsova and Libman 2023).

Other research has explored how environmental and institutional factors shaped economic development in regions of the Russian Empire. For instance, in areas where serf labor was more prevalent, lower levels of labor productivity persisted even 40 years after the abolition of serfdom (Markevich 2014; Markevich and Zhuravskaya 2018). The institution of serfdom itself likely emerged from Russia's unique geopolitical circumstances, such as the constant threat posed by steppe nomads. Defending the state required a large standing army, whose members could not engage in agriculture, thereby necessitating the gradual binding of peasants to the land to sustain this defense system. Indeed, the proportion of serfs in the frontier defense regions during the 17th century was significantly higher – approximately 40% of the population, compared to 14% in the country as a whole (Matranga and Natkhov 2025).

Several studies have addressed regional differences in IND–COL within Russia (e.g., Bakhtigaraeva et al. 2021; Maklasova 2020; Minkov et al. 2023b; Sokolov et al. 2025). However, none have specifically investigated the role of subsistence strategies – particularly agriculture, which has profoundly shaped many aspects of Russian history – in explaining these regional differences. This gap highlights the need for further research to understand how such subsistence strategies, especially the transition from an agrarian to a more industrial and service-based economy, are associated with regional cultural variations in IND–COL across Russia.

Current Study

Grounded in Berry's (2018) ecocultural approach – which emphasizes the adaptive interplay between ecological, cultural, and sociopolitical contexts – this study investigates the historical and contemporary predictors of regional cultural differences in individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) across Russia. The ecocultural framework posits that subsistence strategies, such as agricultural practices, shape cultural and psychological traits through long-term adaptive processes. These influences persist over time, becoming embedded in the social and cultural fabric of societies.

The present study extends prior research on the links between subsistence strategies and cultural orientations. Early work by Berry (1976, 1979) identified associations between types of agriculture and behavioral outcomes such as social conformity and cognitive styles. More recent studies (e.g., Georgas et al. 2006; Minkov et al. 2025; Mishra and Berry 2017; Uskul et al. 2008) have expanded this understanding, showing that irrigation-based agriculture is often associated with higher levels of social conformity and interdependence, whereas dry farming and other forms of subsistence tend to foster greater individual autonomy and analytic thinking. Complementing these findings, the collective activity hypothesis (Uchida et al. 2019) posits that farming-related collective tasks foster shared norms and psychological interdependence, reinforcing collectivist (COL) orientations. Practices such as commu-

nal planting and resource sharing require mutual reliance, embedding these traits in communities even after agriculture ceases to be an economic cornerstone.

While models such as the rice – wheat hypothesis explain cultural variation in regions with specific ecological contrasts, the Russian context requires identifying its own long-term socio-economic adaptations. Despite substantial evidence linking agricultural practices to IND–COL, the role of historical factors – particularly private land ownership – remains underexplored. This gap is especially salient in Russia, a country historically dependent on agriculture, marked by pronounced regional diversity, and shaped by complex socio-political transformations.

Accordingly, this study examines how both historical land ownership patterns and contemporary agricultural employment reflect enduring regional differences in IND–COL, applying Berry's (2018) ecocultural framework to the unique Russian context.

Study 1 investigates the historical prevalence of private land ownership in the late 19th and early 20th centuries as a predictor of regional individualism–collectivism (IND–COL). It posits that regions with greater private ownership were historically associated with higher levels of autonomy and individualism, whereas communal landholding systems were linked to stronger collectivist orientations.

Study 2 examines contemporary factors – particularly the share of the workforce employed in agriculture – to test whether regions with higher agricultural employment today exhibit stronger collectivist tendencies. This reflects the ecocultural premise that subsistence strategies, such as agriculture, continue to shape cultural patterns by fostering interdependence and group cohesion in more agrarian regions.

Together, the two studies assess the long-term coevolution of subsistence strategies and culture in Russia, emphasizing continuity rather than direct causality between historical and contemporary regional characteristics.

Study 1

Study 1, grounded in Berry's (2018) ecocultural framework – which emphasizes long-term adaptation to local socio-ecological conditions – examines whether the prevalence of private land ownership in the late 19th and early 20th centuries is related to regional variation in individualism–collectivism (IND–COL). Although MacFarlane (1978) and Roland (2020) did not explicitly address regional cultures, their research demonstrates that private landownership in Western Europe fostered autonomy and individualism by granting farmers control over their livelihoods.

In contrast, Russia's harsh climatic conditions and labor-intensive agricultural practices produced a markedly different institutional structure – the peasant commune (*obshchina*) – in which land was periodically redistributed among households based on family size and need (Milov 1998). This collective system prioritized group survival over individual autonomy, embedding collectivist norms and reinforcing centralized state control through mechanisms such as serfdom. These communal arrangements were not merely economic institutions but socio-ecological adaptations to local environmental and demographic constraints.

In this study, historical landownership patterns and modern IND–COL levels are treated as indicators of enduring regional differences shaped by these long-term adaptations, without implying direct causality.

Communal land ownership in late-imperial Russia was characterized by collective rights and periodic redistribution: land was allocated according to family size, classified by quality, and divided into scattered strips (*cheresposolitsa* and *melkoposolitsa*), ensuring equitable access but lowering agricultural productivity (Rubakin 1912; Perepelitsyn 2015). Plots could not be inherited, and communal members shared pastures, hayfields, and forests. This system emphasized group cohesion and survival, embedding collectivist norms while constraining individual autonomy. Individuals with more individualistic orientations may have experienced these communal arrangements as restrictive and preferred to acquire private plots, where they could manage and improve the land without the risk of redistribution.

Thus, the regional prevalence of peasant private land ownership does not serve as a direct cause of individualism but as an indicator of socio-ecological conditions that historically permitted individualistic orientations to develop. Study 1 therefore investigates whether these historical patterns correspond to present-day regional differences in IND–COL.

Method

We used two indicators of individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) in our analysis (Figure 1).

The first indicator was the IND index ($M = -0.02$, $SD = 100$, $\min = -400$, $\max = 129$), calculated from regional statistical data such as the percentage of three-generation households and single-person households, the ratio of divorces during a calendar year to the region's average annual population, and other relevant demographic metrics (Gallyamova et al., 2025).

The second indicator measured the level of public endorsement of individualistic values across the regions of the Russian Federation ($M = 0.02$, $SD = 101$, $\min = -435$, $\max = 145$). It was derived from a representative regional survey that included items adapted from the World Values Survey (WVS), such as “Housekeeping is the responsibility of a husband as much as of a wife” and “To what extent can divorce be justified?” (Minkov et al., 2023b).

A detailed description of the construction, normalization, and data sources for both indicators is provided in the Supplementary Material.

For the historical data on land ownership, we used two indicators drawn from the 1907 statistical compendium on landholding in Russia, covering 50 provinces of European Russia (Statistika zemlevladieniya..., 1907).

The first indicator captured the number of individually owned private peasant landholdings in each region, while the second reflected the number of households utilizing allotment land.

The ratio of these two figures served as a measure of the prevalence of peasant private land ownership in each region for the years 1877 ($M = 0.0385$, $SD = 0.0358$, $\min = 0.0003$, $\max = 0.1387$) and 1905 ($M = 0.0531$, $SD = 0.0680$, $\min = 0.0007$, $\max = 0.3044$).

These years were selected not only because of data availability but also because they capture a historically significant period: following the 1861 emancipation of serfs, when private ownership could begin to emerge, and preceding the 1906 Stolypin reforms that relaxed restrictions on withdrawal from communal land systems.

We also incorporated data on the share of urban residents ($M = 10$, $SD = 7$, $\min = 3$, $\max = 41$) and ethnic Russians ($M = 80$, $SD = 18$, $\min = 38$, $\max = 99.7$) in each province as of 1897.

These figures were obtained from the First General Population Census of the Russian Empire (Troinitsky, 1899–1905).

IND index for 83 Russian regions

IND values for 59 Russian regions

Figure 1. IND–COL Indicators by Russian Regions. *Note:* regions marked in dark grey have no data for IND values that can be compared with IND index. *Source:* created by the authors

Details of the methodology used to align historical and modern regional boundaries, as well as descriptions of these and other variables, are provided in the Supplementary Material.

Results

Table 1 and Figure 2 present the correlations among the key variables. The estimates of private land ownership for 1877 and 1905 were strongly correlated ($r = .71, p < .001$), indicating substantial temporal stability. A positive but nonsignificant association was also observed between the 1877 level and its subsequent change by 1905 ($r = .26, p = .084$), suggesting that regions with higher initial levels of private land ownership tended to maintain or slightly increase them, although trajectories varied considerably across regions.

Table 1. Bivariate Correlation between Focal Variables in Study 1

	N	1	2	3	4	5
1. IND index	83					
2. IND values	59	.91***				
3. % of urban population (1897)	70	.03	.07			
4. % of ethnic Russians (1897)	45	.67***	.34	.02		
5. Peasant private land ownership (1877)	44	.55***	.51**	.10	.55***	
6. Peasant private land ownership (1905)	45	.52***	.52**	-.12	.30*	.71***

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Figure 2. Relationships between IND–COL and Peasant Private Land Ownership by Russian Region. Source: created by the authors

The prevalence of peasant private land ownership in both 1877 and 1905 was significantly correlated with contemporary regional indicators of individualism–collectivism (IND–COL).

Specifically, private land ownership in 1877 correlated with the IND index ($r = .55, p < .001$) and with IND values ($r = .51, p = .004$). Similarly, private land ownership in 1905 correlated with the IND index ($r = .52, p < .001$) and with IND values ($r = .52, p = .002$).

The share of urban residents showed no significant correlations with either IND–COL indicator.

By contrast, the proportion of ethnic Russians was positively associated with the IND index ($r = .67, p < .001$), although this relationship did not reach significance for IND values ($r = .34, p = .058$).

It should be noted that the sample size limited statistical power, ranging between .34 and .51 for detecting medium effects ($f^2 = 0.15$). Consequently, the regression results presented in Table 2 should be interpreted with caution. Overall, land ownership in both 1877 and 1905 generally predicted regional IND–COL levels, except in the model using the IND index with the 1877 data.

Table 2. Regression Results Predicting Regional Differences in IND–COL in Russia (Study 1)

	IND index				IND values			
	β	95% CI	<i>p</i>	VIF	β	95% CI	<i>p</i>	VIF
% of urban population (1897)	-.09	[-.32, .15]	.457	1.01	.12	[-.23, .47]	.498	1.05
% of ethnic Russians (1897)	.52***	[.24, .81]	<.001	1.46	.18	[-.24, .60]	.395	1.49
Peasant private land ownership (1877)	.27	[-.02, .55]	.064	1.48	.43*	[.01, .84]	.044	1.44
	$R^2 = .50, F(3, 38) = 12.7***$				$R^2 = .30, F(3, 25) = 3.6^*$			
% of urban population (1897)	-.04	[-.26, .17]	.689	1.02	.21	[-.11, .54]	.191	1.05
% of ethnic Russians (1897)	.57***	[.34, .79]	<.001	1.12	.26	[-.09, .61]	.136	1.17
Peasant private land ownership (1905)	.34**	[.12, .57]	.004	1.13	.47**	[.13, .82]	.009	1.15
	$R^2 = .57, F(3, 39) = 17.0***$				$R^2 = .37, F(3, 26) = 5.1**$			

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

The share of ethnic Russians in 1897 positively predicted the IND index, whereas no significant relationship emerged for IND values. Similarly, the share of urban residents showed no significant associations with either IND–COL measure.

Taken together, these historical predictors explained between 30% and 57% of the variance in IND–COL across regions. No issues of multicollinearity were detected ($VIF < 1.50$), and Durbin–Watson tests indicated no significant autocorrelation in the regression residuals ($DW < 2.29, p > .319$).

Study 2

Study 2 extends Berry's (2018) ecocultural framework to examine whether contemporary differences in agricultural employment continue to correspond with regional patterns of individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) in Russia. Large-scale cross-cultural research has demonstrated that the share of the population engaged in agriculture significantly predicts a variety of cultural, familial, and individual characteristics, both independently and as part of composite indices such as 'Affluence' (Georgas et al., 2006). Originally developed to explore the transition from hunting and gathering to sedentary agricultural societies (Berry, 1976), this framework identifies agricultural involvement as a key marker of societal evolution. Higher engagement in agriculture is associated with closer family proximity, more frequent contact among kin, stronger emotional bonds, interdependent self-construal, higher agreeableness and conscientiousness, and a stronger emphasis on family hierarchy and kinship values – traits characteristic of collectivist (COL) orientations. As societies industrialize and transition to post-industrial stages, agricultural employment declines, accompanied by a shift toward individualist (IND) traits.

In the Russian context, this transition is particularly striking. In 1897, approximately 84% of the population in European Russia were peasants (Moon, 1996), and agriculture remained the dominant sector until the early 20th century (Crisp, 1976). By 2022, only 5.5% of the workforce were employed in agriculture (Agriculture in Russia, 2023). Nonetheless,

substantial regional variation in agricultural employment persists, providing a useful indicator for assessing whether more agrarian regions are characterized by stronger COL orientations.

Agricultural engagement, however, represents only one aspect of broader socio-ecological configurations. Family structures and ethnic composition – both historically linked to subsistence strategies – also reflect regional cultural patterns. For example, regions with higher proportions of ethnic Russians tend to have smaller family sizes and higher IND scores, whereas regions with larger populations of other ethnic groups often exhibit larger households and stronger COL orientations (Minkov et al., 2023b; Sokolov et al., 2025). Given that ethnic Russians are present across nearly all federal subjects, these patterns offer an additional perspective for understanding regional variation in IND–COL.

Method

We used the same two IND–COL indicators as in Study 1. In addition, we incorporated existing statistics on the share of the workforce employed in agriculture ($M = 8, SD = 5, \text{min} = 0.2, \text{max} = 21$) (EMISS, 2023), the proportion of urban residents ($M = 70, SD = 13, \text{min} = 30, \text{max} = 100$) (Rosstat, 2023), and the share of ethnic Russians ($M = 69, SD = 24, \text{min} = 1, \text{max} = 91$) (All-Russian Population Census, 2023). These values were averaged across multiple years to account for temporal fluctuations. Detailed descriptions of these variables and their sources are provided in the Supplementary Material.

Results

Correlations among the focal variables are presented in Table 3 and Figure 3. A strong negative relationship was observed between the share of the workforce in agriculture and both the IND index ($r = -.70, p < .001$) and IND values ($r = -.75, p < .001$). In contrast to the historical urbanization data, both the proportion of urban residents and the share of ethnic Russians exhibited robust positive associations with the IND–COL indicators ($p < .001$).

The sample size provided adequate power to detect medium effects in the regression analyses: power was sufficient for the IND index (.84) but slightly lower for IND values (.69). The regression results, summarized in Table 4, indicate that the share of the workforce in agriculture was a significant negative predictor of both IND–COL measures, whereas the proportion of ethnic Russians was a significant positive predictor. Consistent with the historical analyses, the share of urban residents did not reach statistical significance.

Table 3. Bivariate Correlation between Focal Variables in Study 2

	<i>N</i>	1	2	3	4
1. IND index	83				
2. IND values	59	.91			
3. % of urban population	83	.73	.76		
4. % of ethnic Russians	83	.82	.69	.54	
5. % of workforce in agriculture	83	-.70	-.75	-.80	-.43

Note: All the correlations are at $p < .001$.

Figure 3. Relationships between IND–COL and % of Workforce in Agriculture by Russian Regions. *Source:* created by the authors

Table 4. Regression Results Predicting Regional Differences in IND–COL in Russia (Study 2)

	IND index				IND values			
	β	95% CI	<i>p</i>	VIF	β	95% CI	<i>p</i>	VIF
% of urban population	.14	[-.03, .31]	.099	3.16	.19	[-.03, .42]	.090	3.08
% of ethnic Russians	.60***	[.48, .71]	<.001	1.42	.43***	[.28, .58]	<.001	1.35
% of workforce in agriculture	-.32***	[-.48, -.16]	<.001	2.74	-.44***	[-.65, -.23]	<.001	2.65
	$R^2 = .82, F(3, 79) = 117.3***$				$R^2 = .77, F(3, 55) = 61.9***$			

Note. *** $p < .001$

Together, these predictors explained 82% of the variance in the IND index and 77% of the variance in IND values. Multicollinearity was not a concern ($VIF < 3.17$), and Durbin–Watson tests indicated no significant autocorrelation in the residuals ($DW < 1.78, p > .197$).

Discussion

The present study examined whether historical and contemporary socio-ecological factors are associated with regional variation in individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) across Russia. Consistent with the ecocultural framework (Berry, 1976; Berry, 2018), both historical patterns of landownership and contemporary levels of agricultural employment showed stable relationships with regional cultural differences. These findings align with broader research on the role of subsistence strategies in shaping cultural orientations (e.g., Ang, 2019; Fiszbein et al., 2022; Georgas et al., 2006; Minkov et al., 2025; Mishra & Berry, 2017; Talhelm, 2022; Uchida et al., 2019), as well as studies documenting the association between ethnic composition and IND–COL variation in Russia (Minkov et al., 2023b; Sokolov et al., 2025).

Specifically, regions with a higher prevalence of private land ownership in the late 19th and early 20th centuries tend to exhibit higher contemporary IND levels. While we do not claim single-factor explanations or direct causality, these findings reflect important continuity between long-term socio-economic arrangements and present-day cultural patterns.

This association was particularly evident in the northern and northwestern regions of European Russia, where private landownership was historically concentrated. Although frontier regions such as Siberia and the Far East are often interpreted through the lens of frontier theory (Foa & Nemirovskaya, 2019), our results indicate that historical socio-economic structures – where data are available – also correspond to enduring regional differentiation in cultural orientations.

Although Russia is no longer predominantly agrarian, agriculture continues to play a significant role in the economy. Agricultural land comprises approximately 13% of the country's territory, with the majority located in European Russia (Agriculture in Russia, 2023). Key crops include cereals such as wheat, barley, and corn, while livestock farming – producing meat, milk, and eggs – remains an important sector. These forms of agriculture often rely on stable, close-knit teams, frequently family-based, which may contribute to the stronger collectivist orientation observed in regions with higher agricultural employment.

The persistence of regional group characteristics in Russia is further supported by historical–contemporary continuity in educational outcomes. For instance, districts in the Moskva region in 2012 and 2013 exhibited educational achievements closely mirroring the literacy levels of the peasant population in 1883 (Grigoriev et al., 2015). Similarly, correlations have been observed between regional educational achievements in 2014 and literacy levels at the end of the 19th century (Grigoriev & Shibaev, 2018). Moreover, historical literacy levels across various Russian regions at the end of the 19th century have been linked to the results of the international PISA study on educational achievement in 2015 (Lynn et al., 2017).

Collectively, these findings suggest that certain characteristics of Russian regions have remained stable over time, reflecting long-term patterns of regional differentiation. This continuity is unlikely to be eroded by internal migration, as research indicates that migration in Russia is largely assortative: individuals tend to relocate to regions with culturally or economically similar populations (Perevedentsev, 1975). Such selective migration likely maintains, and may even reinforce, regional distinctions across generations.

The proportion of ethnic Russians in a region consistently correlates with higher levels of individualism, which may reflect long-term socio-economic patterns, such as greater modernization (Sokolov et al., 2025) and smaller family sizes within this group (Minkov et al., 2023b). In contrast, more collectivist-oriented ethnic groups in Russia often maintain larger families and emphasize extended kinship networks and ingroup loyalty. These regional differences in family structure are likely rooted in subsistence strategies: agricultural economies historically fostered larger, interdependent family units to support labor-intensive practices, whereas industrialized and modernized regions, typically associated with smaller-scale farming or other economic activities, favored smaller, more autonomous households (Georgas et al., 2006). This pattern suggests that family size, autonomy, and group cohesion constitute broader, long-term socio-ecological adaptations rather than isolated cultural traits.

Further reinforcing these patterns, consanguinity – marriage between close kin – has been identified as a significant correlate of both democracy and individualism at the cross-cultural level (Woodley of Menie & Bell, 2013). In Russian regions where clan-based structures remain prevalent, such as the national republics of the North Caucasus, traditions of consanguinity and extended family systems persist, supporting collectivist orientations. These social structures prioritize family or clan interests over individual autonomy, discouraging individualistic behaviors that might threaten group cohesion. In contrast, the Central and Northern regions of Russia, characterized by a higher proportion of ethnic Russians, were

historically organized around nuclear families – a pattern already visible in the 19th century (Kravtsova & Libman, 2023). These differences likely reflect long-standing subsistence arrangements, in which larger family units were adaptive in agrarian economies requiring substantial labor inputs, whereas smaller families were better suited to other forms of livelihood.

Urbanization is often associated with higher levels of individualism, as urban environments tend to foster smaller, nuclear family structures and more autonomous social interactions (Georgas et al., 2006; Greenfield, 2009, 2013). However, this association is not universal. In many Western regions, nuclear families and individualistic orientations were already well established before significant urbanization occurred (MacFarlane, 1978), suggesting that urbanization itself is not the primary driver but rather a context that amplifies pre-existing socio-ecological patterns.

From an ecocultural perspective, urbanization can be conceptualized as a proximal condition that facilitates the expression of individualism, while deeper structural determinants – such as subsistence strategies and long-term institutional arrangements – play a more foundational role in shaping cultural orientations. Moreover, the complexity of urban environments does not always yield uniform cultural outcomes; urban settings can also sustain close-knit collectivist groups, particularly among migrant communities or ethnic enclaves (Greenfield, 2009).

These considerations are consistent with our findings, in which urbanization, both historical and contemporary, did not emerge as a significant correlate of regional IND–COL differences in Russia. This likely reflects the fact that urbanization operates within broader, enduring socio-ecological configurations rather than functioning as an independent predictor.

Limitations and Future Research

As with all studies, this research has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. The historical data on private land ownership and the prevalence of communal land use were derived from sources that may not fully capture the complexities of land tenure in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Furthermore, the assumption that county-level historical data can be accurately mapped onto modern regional boundaries introduces a degree of estimation, which may affect the precision of the results. The analysis focused on a limited number of regions within European Russia, potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings to the entire Russian Federation. Additionally, the exclusion of regions with incomplete historical records, such as the Don Host region, restricts the comprehensiveness of the study.

Another limitation concerns the use of contemporary IND–COL indicators. While these measures are robust, they may not fully capture the nuances of cultural change over time. Similarly, reliance on cross-sectional data for current variables such as agricultural employment and urbanization precludes a detailed analysis of temporal dynamics.

Critiques suggesting that our focus on private land ownership overlooks factors such as climate, pathogen prevalence, economic wealth, or religion reflect a misunderstanding of the role of control variables in research. Identifying predictors and establishing causal relationships are fundamentally different tasks, particularly when working with limited historical data. Including numerous control variables indiscriminately often reduces, rather than

enhances, model reliability – a phenomenon referred to as the “myth of control variables” (Carlson & Wu, 2012; Spector & Brannick, 2011). Our deliberate omission of such variables is grounded in this critique. Consistent with Sokolov et al. (2025), introducing additional controls, including climate, population rootedness, and education levels, did not improve explanatory power for IND–COL differences in Russian regions. Instead, these variables were frequently statistically insignificant and introduced multicollinearity, thereby reducing model interpretability. Including superfluous variables in such analyses not only complicates the modeling process but also risks undermining theoretical coherence.

Our approach emphasizes selecting predictors with clear theoretical relevance and empirical justification, grounded in Berry’s (2018) ecocultural framework. This strategy ensures that the findings remain robust and directly aligned with the study’s objectives, avoiding the inclusion of controls that provide minimal explanatory value. While future research using alternative datasets could explore additional factors, the present study represents a focused and methodologically sound effort to address its research questions effectively.

The observed correlations suggest long-term continuity in cultural traits, but further research is needed to examine the mechanisms and potential mediating factors underlying this persistence. Future studies could also explore the experiences of Indigenous populations in Russia, whose unique histories and cultural practices may provide valuable insights into regional variation and historical continuity. Such research would broaden the scope of this work and align it with ongoing efforts to understand the diversity and resilience of cultural traits among Indigenous populations.

Given the available historical data, this analysis likely represents the most comprehensive approach currently possible for examining the relationship between historical socio-economic factors and contemporary cultural differences in IND–COL across Russian regions. The strength of the observed correlations is particularly notable, considering the profound historical events between the Russian Empire and modern Russia. The Soviet era, characterized by radical economic restructuring, extensive regional development, forced resettlement, and ideological campaigns – including the promotion of communist ideals, suppression of religion, and other cultural policies – could have disrupted the continuity of cultural traits. Yet, the persistence of these correlations highlights the enduring influence of historical socio-economic structures on modern cultural characteristics. Despite its limitations, this study provides valuable insights into how historical factors continue to shape regional cultures in Russia today.

Conclusions

This study identified significant historical and contemporary factors associated with regional cultural differences in individualism–collectivism (IND–COL) across Russia. The prevalence of private land ownership in the late 19th and early 20th centuries was strongly correlated with modern IND, suggesting the persistence of cultural traits over time. Contemporary factors, including agricultural employment and ethnic composition – particularly the proportion of ethnic Russians – were also associated with IND–COL variation: regions with higher agricultural engagement exhibited stronger collectivist tendencies, whereas regions with larger proportions of ethnic Russians displayed greater individualism. In contrast, urbanization did not emerge as a significant predictor of IND–COL differences, indicating that while it may be linked to individualism, it does not appear to play a primary role.

Overall, these findings highlight the enduring influence of historical socio-economic structures and contemporary subsistence strategies on regional cultural orientations in Russia, emphasizing the importance of long-term ecological, economic, and demographic factors in shaping the cultural landscape.

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Ethics Statement

This study complied with COPE and APA ethical standards. Procedures conformed to Russian regulations; no formal ethics clearance was required as the research did not involve medical data.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Supplementary material 1

Methodology

Methodology for calculating variables used in the study.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.10.e151080.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Dataset

Dataset containing variables used in the study.

Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.10.e151080.suppl2>

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